

COST Action

Progress Report at 24 months

(21/09/2022 to 21/09/2024)

CA21161: A new ecosystem of early music studies

The Action was approved by the Committee of Senior Officials (CSO) on 27-5-2022 and has the MoU reference COST 075/22.

This report shows the data entered into e-COST to enable the Action Chair to verify the completeness and accuracy of the report with the MC prior to submitting the report via e-COST in fulfilment of the rules for COST Action Management, Monitoring and Final Assessment.

Action leadership and participants

Leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Chair	Dr Philippe VENDRIX	vendrix@univ-tours.fr	France

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Action Vice-Chair	Dr Rebekah Ahrendt	r.s.ahrendt@uu.nl	Netherlands

Working groups

#	WG Title	# of participants	WG Leader	Country*
1	Education	110	Dr Aleksandra Pister-Gainiene aleksandrapister@yahoo.de	Lithuania
2	Sources	143	Dr Grzegorz Joachimiak grzegorz.joachimiak@uwr.edu.pl	Poland
3	Publications	115	Dr Andrea Puentes Blanco apuentes@imf.csic.es	Spain
4	Performances	101	Dr Kalina Tomova kalina.tomova@yahoo.com	Bulgaria
5	Policies	52	Dr Brianne Dolce bridolce@gmail.com	Netherlands

Other key leadership positions

Position	Name	Contact details	Country*
Science Communication Coordinator	Dr Marten Noorduin	Marten.Noorduin@mh-luebeck.de	Germany
GH Scientific Representative	Philippe VENDRIX	vendrix@univ-tours.fr	France

* The country displayed is:

- for the Action Chair, the country that nominated that person to the Management Committee before they were elected Action Chair;
- for the Action Vice-Chair the country that nominated the person as a Management Committee Member,
- for all other leadership positions, if the person is a MC Member the country displayed is the country of nomination, otherwise it is the country of the person's primary work affiliation.

Participants

COST members having accepted the MoU

AL	22/06/2022	AM	09/01/2023	AT	22/06/2022	BE	22/06/2022	BA	22/06/2022
BG	22/06/2022	HR	22/06/2022	CY	22/06/2022	CZ	22/06/2022	DK	22/06/2022
EE	22/06/2022	FI	22/06/2022	FR	22/06/2022	GE	22/06/2022	DE	22/06/2022
EL	22/06/2022	HU	22/06/2022	IS	22/06/2022	IE	22/06/2022	IL	22/06/2022
IT	22/06/2022	LV	22/06/2022	LT	22/06/2022	LU	22/06/2022	MT	22/06/2022
MD	22/06/2022	ME	22/06/2022	NL	22/06/2022	MK	22/06/2022	NO	22/06/2022
PL	22/06/2022	PT	22/06/2022	RO	22/06/2022	RS	22/06/2022	SK	22/06/2022
SI	22/06/2022	ZA	22/06/2022	ES	22/06/2022	SE	22/06/2022	CH	22/06/2022
TR	22/06/2022	UA	22/06/2022	UK	22/06/2022				

Other participants

Institution Name	Country

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Summary

The main aim and objective of the Action is to

EarlyMuse intends to chart new paths that will strengthen the unique place of early music in Europe. It will therefore be a matter of confronting the challenges that arise from different vantage points: (1) scientific, (2) educational, (3) structural and professional, (4) economic and societal.

During its first two years the Action progressed the achievement of this as described below

EarlyMuse fostered the development of a geographically inclusive community focused on historical musicology. It addressed topics related to scientific practices (WG Publications), the status of the discipline in higher education and research (WG Education), the modes of deploying shared tools (WG Sources), and the relationships with the field of research-creation (WG Performance). Finally, it aimed to raise awareness within its community about European issues and to consider ways to engage with public policymakers (WG Policies).

Now bringing together 263 members from 39 countries, EarlyMuse has organized its activities around meetings and short scientific missions that have strengthened connections among researchers from diverse backgrounds. These activities have resulted in publications, most of which are freely accessible on EarlyMuse's own website. They have also invited researchers to combine their efforts to engage with other EU initiatives (Creative Europe, European Cloud for Cultural Heritage, Marie Curie Network).

The next two years, 2025 and 2026, will transform the reflections and investigations of 2023 and 2024 into concrete outputs: articles, notes, policy briefs, and reports. There is no real danger, but there is an obligation to remain vigilant in order to listen to as many voices as possible, thereby strengthening collective initiatives to move beyond the fundamentally individualistic conception of the discipline.

The Action will implement the following measures in the coming two years to overcome any issues identified in this report as potentially endangering the achievement of the objectives of the Action

There is no real danger as such, but constant attention must be paid to ensure geographical balance, the contribution of young researchers, and gender balance. A junior researcher from Croatia has been appointed to inform us on gender equality issues within our action and also beyond, in the professional sector.

Action website

<https://earlymuse.eu/>

Achievement of MoU objectives, deliverables and additional outputs/ achievements

MoU objectives

Please self-assess and describe the level of achievement of each MoU objective. For any MoU objective that is 25% or less achieved, please add an explanation.

Mou objective	Analysis of the higher education and scientific landscape of early music: the objective will be to describe and analyse the situation of early music by comparing the academic and non-academic worlds, in Europe. What impulses are modulating this landscape today?
Type of objective	2.a Building a community around a topic of scientific and/or socio-economic relevance, allowing for knowledge exchange and the development of a joint research agenda
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>Historical musicology struggles to be identified as a professional field. There are many reasons for this. First, there is the diversity of workplaces (from researchers or teachers at a university to a dramaturg in an opera or an advisor at a publishing house). Then, there's the often multifaceted nature of a musicologist's career, as they may also be performers. Finally, there is the flexibility needed within the sub-disciplines of the musicological field: how to distinguish between historical musicology, music theory, and ethnomusicology. To address the question of professional status in the most flexible, open, and inclusive way, a proposal has been made to conduct three-phase surveys. The first phase is dedicated to higher education institutions and research organizations. The second addresses artistic teaching institutions. The third will focus on non-academic environments. The first survey will lead to a report that, while not exhaustive, covers a significant part of Europe. The second started in 2024 and will continue into 2025. The third will begin at the end of 2025.</p> <p>A key challenge for these surveys is access to data. Institutional websites are often imprecise and only consider the current situation. Some countries do not have a list of defended theses. Caution is necessary when compiling information to present it to readers.</p> <p>The ultimate goal of the first two surveys is to provide a snapshot of historical musicology in Europe between 2015 and 2025, as a way to confer visibility on a professional field that suffers from its dispersion.</p> <p>An initial 35-page report is being circulated among the 260 members of the EarlyMuse initiative to provide the most accurate data. This report will be published in open access on the EarlyMuse website and will be widely publicized within the international community: Levaux, Christophe, Philippe Vendrix & Adam Whittaker (ed.), <i>Historical musicology in European universities, research organisations and scientific academies: a preliminary survey</i>, Brussels, 2024.</p>

Mou objective	The meaning and strength of early music: its modalities of operation are no longer those of the past decades. Their presence is still affirmed in the academic world. However, the music industries are seeking to offer new models.
Type of objective	1.j Dissemination of research results to stakeholders (excluding specific input in view of knowledge application)
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	Many discussions within our actions have focused on the ambiguities surrounding the very concept of Early Music. Researchers have also highlighted the difficulties of this concept, particularly in studies on the status of historical musicology in European universities. It is evident that the concept is borrowed from the world of musical practice and does not belong to the conceptual vocabulary. However, its symbolic strength

associated with the practice of historical musicology supports its use. Nothing better demonstrates the utility of the concept than the title of REMA, the European Early Music Network, arguably the main non-academic partner with which EarlyMuse has worked during the first two years. EarlyMuse has contributed to REMA's annual meetings. The coordinator of stakeholder relations within the action has maintained a consistent relationship with this organization, which brings together musicians, broadcasters, and some researchers. After two years of exchanges, it is still not possible to present a common project that would associate the two networks, REMA and EarlyMuse. However, several clear orientations emerge from the discussions: (1) it is necessary to work together in the face of platforms (2) it is important to identify new and innovative paths for communication in both research and artistic creation by using new models (3) it will likely be effective to find a common vocabulary for all professionals, whether from science or practice, in order to coordinate efforts at the European level. Creative Europe is the EU program that allows researchers to work on common projects with practitioners. The same applies to initiatives that focus on the CCIs (cultural and creative industries).

Mou objective	Preservation of musical heritage and accessibility to resources: an essential step towards enabling early music to participate in the CCI dynamic is the development and construction of a platform that will enable the richness, diversity and complexity of the early music field to be visible and accessible.
Type of objective	1.e Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>One of the primary goals of the WG2 SOURCES working group within EarlyMuse is to emphasize the value of Europe's musical heritage. This involves not only maintaining, preserving, and safeguarding sources (which is essential), but also encouraging academic, artistic, and educational communities to engage in continuous hermeneutic actions. Despite the availability of new technologies and their use in daily work, unforeseen and crisis situations still arise, requiring various procedures and so-called "emergency solutions". We are convinced that preserving musical sources will allow us to retain the centuries-old cultural heritage and memory of our past, which shapes European identity. Consequently, this becomes a priority guide in charting new horizons.</p> <p>In light of the principles expressed in the Memorandum of Understanding, our efforts have thus far focused on identifying endangered collections and corpora of early music, as well as criteria for cataloging musical works. A key factor supporting these actions is the close collaboration with the main RISM editorial offices in Frankfurt am Main and the RISM Digital Center in Bern. During workshops in Lisbon and Wrocław, we dedicated much attention to the methods of processing musical sources, making them accessible, and, most importantly, identifying source collections that urgently require conservation support and digitization.</p> <p>1) Describing methods for identifying and cataloging endangered musical sources (including those in Ukraine),</p> <p>2) Establishing a protocol for information exchange with RISM.</p> <p>To effectively prepare for the specificity of the upcoming WG2 community workshops (over 140 participants), a preliminary online meeting was held in February 2024, which also aimed to gather data from two surveys. These surveys provided insight into the areas in which WG2 members (musicologists, music theorists, performers, librarians and archivists, educators, cultural managers) work with early music sources, their expectations regarding cooperation with the IT sector, and the direction we aim to take in the project and for the Wrocław workshops.</p>

Mou objective	Early music: societal dimension, policy making and business. A two-pronged strategy: first to raise the profile of the field and create awareness of the challenges and opportunities it presents, and second to provide decision makers with the
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	understanding they need to realize the field's potential.
Type of objective	1.g Input to stakeholders (e.g. standardization body, policy-makers, regulators, users), excluding commercial applications
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>Members from all the WGs have coordinated their efforts to lay the foundations for a new European infrastructure (modeled on DARIAH or EUROPEANA) that would be specifically dedicated to music in all its aspects. Europe boasts a rich and diverse musical heritage, deeply interwoven with its cultural identity. This heritage, spanning centuries and encompassing a wide range of traditions, genres, and practices, represents a fundamental part of Europe's past, present, and future. However, accessing this wealth of musical knowledge is often fragmented and inefficient, particularly across borders. Without a dedicated infrastructure to support music research, Europe risks losing invaluable opportunities to fully harness its cultural resources. Establishing a comprehensive Pan-European Music Research Infrastructure (PEMRI) would address this challenge. This infrastructure must interlink, sustain and preserve all richness of music-related knowledge, including musical scores, audiovisual recordings, instruments, and academic data. Such an infrastructure will enable cross-border collaboration in the digital age and position Europe as a global leader in innovative musicological research, ensuring that its rich musical traditions are preserved and fully leveraged for future innovations and public benefit. The collective work on this topic, carried out in WG meetings and special working meetings, will appear in a policy brief to be disseminated to relevant stakeholders in 2025.</p>

Mou objective	Creating a multidisciplinary research network. The aim is not to exist as an autonomous force, but to coordinate dialogue in order to understand all aspects of the scientific field and its cultural implications.
Type of objective	2.c Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>Beyond epistemological questions (multidisciplinarity, the role of digital technology), it became clear from the first EarlyMuse meetings that the primary work should consist of (1) clearly identifying the professional sector of "musicology" and (2) working on knowledge dissemination tools that would allow better visibility of the discipline by connecting it with a broader readership. These reflections led to a proposal for a new mode of publication (work primarily from WG3).</p> <p>The field of musicology is experiencing a dramatic transformation, fueled by the rise of digital technologies. From massive digitization projects to the explosion of online music platforms, these advancements offer exciting opportunities for research and communication. However, they also present a unique set of challenges, requiring a shift in how we think about scholarship and publication. As we navigate this new landscape, it's crucial to ensure that musicological research remains accessible, impactful, and inclusive. Traditional musicological publications, often limited to text and notation, struggle to adequately convey the richness and complexity of musical research. The integration of multimedia elements, such as sound and video recordings, poses significant challenges. Funding, technological expertise, and the need to ensure long-term accessibility are just a few of the hurdles to overcome. Consider, for instance, the daunting task of archiving a vast digital collection of recordings, ensuring its preservation and accessibility for future generations.</p> <p>This shift towards multimedia also necessitates a rethink of our approach to the scholarship itself. How do we effectively integrate multimedia elements into our research without sacrificing scholarly rigor? How do we ensure that these elements enhance, rather than detract from, our arguments? These are critical questions that we must grapple with as we move forward. The transition to a digital landscape also highlights existing inequalities within the field. Researchers from under-resourced institutions or those working in less widely spoken languages often face significant barriers in publishing and sharing their work. Access to funding, cutting-edge technology, and peer-reviewed journals can be limited, hindering their ability to</p>

	<p>contribute to the broader scholarly conversation.</p> <p>Furthermore, the disparity between performance-based doctorates and traditional research doctorates requires attention. Many institutions award doctorates in music performance, where the research component often takes a backseat to practical skills development. While performance-based research is valuable, it often receives less recognition within the academic world, leaving these scholars at a disadvantage. So, how can we navigate these challenges and unlock the full potential of digital musicology? The answer lies in a multifaceted approach that addresses both the technical and the social aspects of this transformation. The WG Publications has outlined the major challenges and the technical solutions which should be transformed in a detailed roadmap during the year 3.</p>
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Mou objective	Scientific dissemination and clustering. The aim is to publish studies that will nourish the public debate while allowing the emergence of new paradigms to address the political dimension of early music, and beyond any form of music through the methodology that will be implemented.
Type of objective	1.i Dissemination of research results to the general public
Level of progress	0 - 25%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>WG3 Edition has written a critical journal article on the future of monumental music editions. This open-access article (https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998) presents fresh perspectives on challenges monumental editions face in the twenty-first century along with current efforts to address them. It provides a range of viewpoints, approaches, and case studies about the current state of the most emblematic European Monumenta collections and how their editorial boards are imagining and creating a sustainable future for these editorial enterprises that had, and still have, a fundamental role in shaping how we see and understand today the history of the European music.</p> <p>A statement paper is expected to be published soon on the new model of publishing musicological works. Similarly, the WG Policies has addressed new issues concerning the European Cloud for Cultural Heritage to encourage (1) mobilization of the community to integrate this dynamic and (2) the creation of tools to make it operational. These topics were central to the meetings in Zagreb and Malaga in 2024.</p>

Mou objective	Career and regulations EarlyMuse intends to confront the question of careers. They differ according to the genre, the country and the nature of the profession. It intends to work on the place of women, the professional potential of new graduates.
Type of objective	2.e Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action
Level of progress	26 - 50%
Description of progress with achieving the MoU objective	<p>The issue of careers is at the heart of the work conducted by WG1 Education. An initial large-scale survey has been conducted among universities and research organizations in Europe. A second one is underway with conservatories and similar institutions. This survey will require extensive effort, widely involving the EarlyMuse community. Finally, a third survey will cover non-academic professional environments that employ doctors in musicology. The overall objective is clearly the identification of a professional sector, as musicology does not appear in any OECD document. However, it will not only involve documents intended for decision-makers or analysts at the national or European levels. It will also provide useful information for colleagues who, as the surveys show, work in conditions and contexts that are too heterogeneous to foster networked research in a calm manner.</p> <p>The first survey will be available on the website of EarlyMuse: Levaux, Christophe, Philippe Vendrix & Adam Whittaker (ed.), <i>Historical musicology in European universities, research organisations and scientific academies: a preliminary survey</i>,</p>

36p. The second should be published by July 2025.

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Deliverables

This section covers only deliverables that were foreseen for the Action, not additional outputs that were generated during the Action (these additional outputs will be added in the following section). Please select and comment on the progress with achieving each deliverable.

For deliverables that are:

- Delivered, please provide proof to enable the Action Rapporteur to confirm the delivery
- Not delivered but delivery is foreseen within 2 years please explain how the delivery will be achieved
- Not foreseen to be delivered please explain why not

Deliverable	Reprrt on the structure and nature of early music education in conservatories and universities.		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Explanation	Part 1 dedicated to universities is finished and under revision (all members of the action are asked to read and check input). Part 2 dedicated to conservatories is in progress (should be finished by July 2025). and the third one on non-academic opportunities should be ready by spring 2026. The goal is to have a report by the end of action.		

Deliverable	Analysis (report) of target collections, analyzing benefits of cataloguing and digitization [months 30, 48].		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Explanation	A report has been produced by WG Sources. It is under revision and should be published on our website soon. It is dedicated to the dynamic of RISM and endangered sources.		

Deliverable	Study on alternative publication formats and standards for music research and digital music editions.		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	45
Explanation	As for today a fist "position paper" has been written and is submitted for publication in "Musicological Brainfood," a professional blog of the International Musicological Society. A full description of the new model of publication in planned to be distributed by mid-2025.		

Deliverable	Planning and design of a comprehensive online resource (as part of the project's platform) to enhance the career advancement opportunities of musicians devoted to early music [months 24, 42].		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	42
Explanation	Progress has been made in surveying the needs of the professional sector, though we have encountered challenges due to the lack of comprehensive data sources. Our partnership with REMA is key to achieving this goal due to their network within the performance field, and we have already achieved good results through mutual exchange at meetings and via an STSM.		

Deliverable	Survey of national / European cultural policies and how they interact / affect early music; overview of support for early music [months 24, 36]; white paper on how to maximize the potential of early music from a policy perspective [month 48].		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Explanation	WG5 has organised a meeting in Malaga (September 2024) following a first meeting in March 2024 in Zagreb. Three policy briefs are almost completed: 1. A brief for explaining how it is crucial to study the European musical heritage and how our community of musicologists is ready to embark on the European Cloud of Cultural Heritage representing a fundamental field of intangible heritage. 2. A brief to express the importance of developing a scholarly approach to music as a sector in the cultural and creative industries. 3. A brief to initiate the idea of having a European infrastructure dedicated to music.		

Deliverable	Regular publications within the consortium and communication to the target communities [months 13-48].		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Proof of progress with achieving the deliverable	https://earlymuse.eu/publications/		
Explanation	In progress. Different types of publications are available on https://earlymuse.eu/publications/		

Deliverable	Early music education : data collection by ECIs at various institutions (academic and non-academic).		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	18
Explanation	See deliverable 4 which states the difficulties of gathering consolidated data.		

Deliverable	Design of a comprehensive online resource (as part of the project's platform) to enhance the career advancement opportunities of musicians devoted to early music.		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	42
Explanation	Same as div. 4 and div. 7. Surveys are in progress and should help nourish a strategy for careers.		

Deliverable	Paper(s) on how to assess alternative publication formats in the academic context.		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	36
Explanation	A first statement paper has been sent to the International Musicological Society. A complete description should be available by mid 2025.		

Deliverable	Prospects for creation of new outlets (hybrid journals and other alternatives). Criteria and digital tools involved in the online publication of music research and digital music editions.		
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Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	45
Explanation	All WGs have worked on defining what could be an ideal infrastructure for music at the EU level. The policy brief on that topic should be available by spring 2025.		

Deliverable	White paper on how to maximize the potential of early music from a policy perspective.		
Progress with achieving deliverable	Not delivered, but expected before end of Action	Month deliverable due	48
Explanation	Three topics are presently under study for a white paper to be pertinent. It included proposal for the integration in the European Cloud for Heritage, the creation of an infrastructure and the arguments for identifying a professional sector Musicology.		

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Additional outputs / achievements

Co-authored Action publications

Please enter below ONLY publications (including publications that are submitted but not yet accepted):

- that are on the topic of the Action, and
- that are co-authored by at least two Action participants from two countries participating in the Action, and
- for which the Action networking was necessary.

Please pay special attention to the COST Excellence and Inclusiveness policy and ensure the inclusion of publications with authors from COST Inclusiveness Target Countries (ITCs), from the underrepresented gender in the Action and from Early Career Investigators/Young researchers.

	Bibliographic data	Countries participating in the Action among authors	Open Access	COST cited?	COST funds?	Relevance to H2020 Societal challenge	Peer Reviewed?
1	doi:10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998		Other	Y	Y		Y

Projects resulting from Action activities

Please enter below all the projects on the topic of the Action resulting from Action activities, involving at least one Action participant, and for which the Action networking was necessary.

The Action reported 0 project(s) and 1 proposal(s) resulting from the Action networking.

#	Title	Countries participating in the Action among proposers	Main proposer name	Funder	Amount	Call identifier	Relevance to H2020 Societal Challenge

Other outputs / achievements

Please enter below any additional outputs/ achievements on the topic of the Action that contribute to the COST mission: “COST enables break-through scientific developments leading to new concepts and products and thereby contributes to strengthen Europe’s research and innovation capacities”, and for which the Action networking was necessary (e.g. a patent, standards, white paper).

Output / achievement description	Dependence of achievement on the Action networking

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Impacts

Please describe the impacts (the short- to long-term scientific, technological, and / or socioeconomic changes produced by a COST Action, directly or indirectly, intended or unintended) that have resulted, or might result, from the Action in the following table (one impact per line).

Description of the impact, i.e. what will change, and for whom, as a result of what the Action achieved	Type of impact	Timing of impact
From a scientific perspective, EarlyMuse has begun to identify new directions for the future of musicological research. By focusing on publication methods and approaches to sources, the involved researchers have identified avenues that have been published in a peer-reviewed journal and in reports that are widely distributed. This work is too recent to quantitatively measure its impact. At most, the metrics concerning the article published in a journal indicate a genuine interest from researchers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific / Technological 	Foreseen by the end of the Action
EarlyMuse aims to tackle two economic challenges. The first concerns the future methods of publication, and the second involves the conditions for a dialogue between musicology and the cultural and creative industries. For the first, milestones have been set, and feedback will be assessed once a statement paper is published (before the end of 2024). For the second, the field is considerably more complex, particularly due to the difficulty in establishing dialogue with music distribution platforms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Economic 	Foreseen by the end of the Action
On the societal level, the impacts will be measurable once the work on the professional sector is completed and when the new mode of dissemination for musicological research is established. The first point is crucial as it would allow for the inclusion of the 'musicology' sector in OECD statistics. Starting in October 2024, EarlyMuse has appointed a leader for gender issues. A young researcher from Croatia will oversee this central theme, particularly with regard to academic careers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Societal 	Foreseen by the end of the Action

Please describe how the Action is advancing the careers, skills and network of researchers, including ECIs (for example: joint supervision of graduate and PhD students, research exchanges not funded by the Action, collaborations, Training Schools with ECTS accreditation, joint projects and jobs prospects).

The Action organized a workshop on policy briefs in Malaga in 2024, which included instruction on how to write and disseminate policy briefs to relevant stakeholders. The workshop included 19 participants, of which 7 were ECIs. More powerful, though, have been the STSMs organized by the Action over the last two years, which have directly resulted in career opportunities, the acquisition of new skills, and the expansion of researchers' networks. The first year of the Action saw 14 STSM recipients: 7 were from ITCs and 9 were ECIs. In 2024, EarlyMuse sponsored 36 STSM recipients, of whom 19 were ECIs and 14 were from ITCs. We have also distributed a total of 16 ITC Conference Grants, enabling our colleagues to share work related to our Action.

The career benefits are mainly to researchers with the following amount of experience after their PhD: ≤ 8 years.

Which of the stakeholders described in the "Plan for involving the most relevant stakeholders" in the Action's MoU have been engaged and how? What additional stakeholders have been, or will be, engaged and how?

The most important stakeholders to be engaged thus far include REMA, RISM, and RILM. With REMA we have organized STSMs and we have joined in two REMA meetings. In November 2024 we will have a leadership meeting with REMA and also the European Association of Conservatories to establish roadmaps for educational cooperation. RISM has hosted STSMs; representatives from RISM have joined various WG meetings to help shape the nature of our cooperation. RILM has similarly been present at WG meetings and involved in working with WG 3 on the challenges of editions in the digital age. In the future, we intend to engage other stakeholders in the international

nonprofit field, including organizations that are actively working toward shaping EU cultural policy. We have already made initial contact with the European Music Council, Culture Action Europe and Europa Nostra at events that they have hosted in Brussels and elsewhere. We intend to organize meetings with them by 2026 to establish partnerships that can outlast this Action.

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Dissemination and exploitation of Action results (other than co-authored Action publications listed previously)

Please describe the Action's dissemination and exploitation approach as well as all activities undertaken to ensure dissemination and exploitation of the Action results and the effectiveness of these activities.

Dissemination and exploitation approach of the Action

EarlyMuse has a team responsible for disseminating information about its activities and research results. Social media platforms are activated and regularly updated (Facebook and X). The website is enriched with reports, video clips, and brief presentations that provide insights into the work and actions. See <https://earlymuse.eu/> For the year 2025 (year 3), there are plans to intensify EarlyMuse's participation in international conferences to present the results of the work conducted by the various working groups.

Dissemination

Dissemination meetings funded by the Action (possible only until 31st October 2021)

Title of Dissemination meeting	Meeting date	Meeting country	Action participant	Event name and hyperlink to the website	Title of presentation	Description of added value to the Action
N/A						

Other dissemination activities

E.g. participation to non-Action meetings, e.g. EU Parliament, meetings with policy makers, experts in the field, regional authorities.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome	Hyperlink
Conference organised by third party in Dublin (Music, Musicology and Academic Responsibilities in the 21st Century)	Scholars working all over the worlds on different aspects of musicology and facing different issues with academic responsibility of the field.	A first dialogue between EarlyMuse and scholars coming from all over the world.	https://www.ucd.ie/music/newsandevents/conferences/musicmusicologyandacademicresponsibilities/
Conference organised by the Royal Musical Association ofr its 150th anniversary (London)	Scholars and music publishers coming from the UK (young and senior).	A round table on the future of music editin which allows EarlyMuse to present the results of the WP Publication (monumental editions, publications of the future in musicology). EarlyMuse is invited to particpate in a reserach program supported	https://rma150.wordpress.com

by AHRC in connection with Musica
Britanica.

Exploitation activities

Please describe below any activities undertaken to ensure exploitation (use, in particular in a commercial context) of the Action's achievements.

Item/activity	Target audience	Outcome
N/A		

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Other matters

This section is confidential to the Management Committee, the Action Rapporteur and the COST Association, and is not included in the version of the report that is published on the COST website.

Difficulties in implementing the Action

If any difficulties are experienced in the implementation of the Action (e.g. imbalances of participation across the Working Groups, inactive country representatives) please describe these below. Please also describe the efforts made by the MC to address these.

An important part of the action's work has specifically involved explaining the role of COST in the European research landscape. The effect has been positive: in no time, the action has brought together 263 researchers from 39 countries. Not everyone is engaged in the same way, but there is a genuine willingness to work collectively. The issue of communication is not simple either. We have a website that already requires quite a bit of work. Being present on social media does not seem fundamentally useful. However, EarlyMuse is now invited to present its results at international conferences—cautiously in 2024 but more intensively in 2025.

Endangerment Measures

Taking into account the issues identified throughout this report, please summarise the measures the Action will implement in the coming two years to overcome any issues identified as potentially endangering the achievement of the objectives of the Action.

There is no real danger as such, but constant attention must be paid to ensure geographical balance, the contribution of young researchers, and gender balance. A junior researcher from Croatia has been appointed to inform us on gender equality issues within our action and also beyond, in the professional sector.

Suggestions for improvements to COST framework/ procedures

The mandate of the Scientific Committee includes providing advice to the COST Committee of Senior Officials on possible improvements to the COST framework. Please describe below any improvements that you believe should be made to the COST framework.

EarlyMuse benefits from very effective scientific and logistical support from COST. All our questions are answered promptly. That said: We encourage COST to consider revising the current policy regarding the definition of "young" researchers. The problem especially touches our Action because many people come to our field via a long journey, and careers are difficult to launch. This means that many do not undertake or finish the PhD until they are already over or near 40 years old. We therefore could wish that COST would adopt the same principle as the ERC, for example, and define an early-career researcher based on the date of the PhD, rather than chronological age.

Sustaining the network beyond the Action

Are there any plans to sustain the network beyond the end of the Action?

YES

Please describe how the network will be sustained beyond the end of the Action.

Already, Philippe Vendrix has ensured the inclusion of the music field in the ECHOES project, which forms the foundation of the European Cloud for Cultural Heritage. At the same time, EarlyMuse is working on the foundations of a European music infrastructure that will be able to address the challenges posed by the New Bauhaus in the field of music creation and study in Europe.

Emerging topics/ developments in the field of the Action

Please describe any emerging topics or potentially important future developments identified during the Action and that could potentially be addressed by future COST activities such as Actions S&T Conferences or Exploratory Workshops.

An important emerging theme is the role of musicological research--and our object of study, music--in the development of the European Cloud for Heritage. As the most important type of intangible heritage, musical heritage presents many opportunities for innovating methods and technologies in the Cloud. Yet there are many challenges as well, ranging from the copyright issues related to audiovisual recordings, to the continued challenges of Optical Music Recognition, to the most sustainable and accurate way to create a digital twin of a fragmentary musical score. Yet we are not the only field to be busy with these questions of intangible heritage, and we could imagine that the technological and philosophical issues associated with "recording" intangible heritage could be fruitful terrain for S&T Conferences or Exploratory Workshops bringing together humanists and technologists, for example.

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Annex 1: Types of objectives

1 - Coordination of scientific and technological activities at a European level

- 1.a - Development of a common understanding/definition of the subject matter
- 1.b - Coordination of information seeking, identification, collection and/or data curation
- 1.c - Coordination of experimentation or testing
- 1.d - Comparison and/or performance assessment of a theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.e - Development of knowledge needing international coordination, pertaining to a new or improved theory, model, methodology, technology or technique
- 1.f - Achievement of a specific tangible output that cannot be achieved without international coordination (e.g. due to practical issues such as database availability, language barriers, availability of infrastructure or know-how, etc.)
- 1.g - Input to stakeholders (e.g. standardization body, policy-makers, regulators, users), excluding commercial applications
- 1.h - Input for future market applications (including cooperation with private enterprises)
- 1.i - Dissemination of research results to the general public
- 1.j - Dissemination of research results to stakeholders (excluding specific input in view of knowledge application)

2 - Community building

- 2.a - Building a community around a topic of scientific and/or socio-economic relevance, allowing for knowledge exchange and the development of a joint research agenda
- 2.b - Building a community around a new or emerging field of research
- 2.c - Bridging separate fields of science/disciplines to achieve breakthroughs that require an interdisciplinary approach
- 2.d - Acting as a stakeholder platform or trans-national practice community, pertaining to a certain area of socio-economical or societal application, or to a certain market sector
- 2.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action

Annex 2: Dimensions of successes

1 - Breakthroughs

- 1.a - Scientific breakthrough
- 1.b - Technological breakthrough
- 1.c - Breakthrough in socio-economic or societal applications

2 - Policy contribution

- 2.a - Contribution to regulatory policy
- 2.b - Contribution to environmental, infrastructural or agricultural policy
- 2.c - Contribution to economic or socio-economic policy
- 2.d - Contribution to social, cultural or legal policy

3 - Capacity building

- 3.a - Building capacity in an existing field of science and technology
- 3.b - Building capacity in bridging separate fields of science and technology
- 3.c - Building capacity in a new or emerging field of science and technology
- 3.d - Building capacity in valorising and implementing advances and applications in science and technology
- 3.e - Building capacity in the demographic inclusiveness of networks in science and technology, including representation of newly established research groups, Early-Career Investigators, the under-represented gender and teams from countries/regions with less capacity in the field of the Action

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